

Executive Summary

AmazonFACE Engagement Workshop

AMAZONFACE

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Overview

This document systematises the main points discussed at the first AmazonFACE engagement workshop focused on the interface between science(s), public policies and society. The objective is to support decision-makers, managers, and researchers with a direct synthesis on consensus, challenges, and ways to strengthen the use of scientific knowledge in the formulation, implementation, and evaluation of climate policies.

Key Messages

- **Science and public policy should engage in an integrated and ongoing dialogue.** The incorporation of evidence into climate policies is a non-linear process and requires institutional articulation, translation capacity, and permanent interaction mechanisms.
- **Data needs to be actionable** to guide implementation. Scientific evidence must be translated into clear, accessible information to support decision-making and execution, especially at the state and municipal levels.
- **Well-designed policies can help reduce emissions and increase resilience.** There is convergence on the importance of policies based on the best available science, with monitoring and evaluation throughout their implementation.
- **Interministerial integration is a condition for effectiveness.** The workshop reinforced the need for integrated planning and coordination between sectors to address climate change and associated crises.
- **The Amazon is strategic for mitigation and adaptation.** The biome and its peoples are central to the climate agenda and require territorially sensitive approaches.
- Solutions require time, social engagement, and recognition of the various sciences at stake. The importance of involving society and recognising the territories and the knowledges of Indigenous Peoples, Quilombolas¹, Traditional and Local Communities as active parts of the solutions was highlighted.

¹ **Quilombolas** are Brazilians of African descent, who established communities called *quilombos*, formed by escaped enslaved people seeking freedom from Brazil's brutal slave system.

Gaps

Opportunities

Linearity / technocracy	Reposition the interface from “production → use” to a procedural and co-produced model, with interaction from the definition of problems and priorities.
Technical governance	Expand governance to include social, territorial, political, and ethical dimensions, making explicit asymmetries (such as race and gender) to strengthen legitimacy and effectiveness.
Amazon-object	The Amazon as a subject-territory, integrating science, ways of life, and local knowledge as a structuring part of climate governance.
Negotiating priorities	Create mechanisms to negotiate priorities between research and public policies, with transparency about choices, limitations, and implications.
Linear interface between science(s) - Politics	Move towards co-production that integrates indigenous, traditional, and local science and sciences as constitutive of the interface with public policy, rather than merely advisory.

As part of **Research Area 5 - Socio-environmental**, the AmazonFACE program is committed to continuing to build opportunities for engagement between science and public policy, in a structured and continuous way, to seek actionable solutions for decision-makers in ways that respond to the needs and desires of affected communities, especially in the Amazon. To this end, we are planning activities over the next few years to continue contributing to this collective effort.

Next Steps

- 2026 (Manaus): territorial workshop to deepen desired futures, challenges, and actions to strengthen the science(s)–policy–society interface in the Amazon.
- 2027 (Brasília): national workshop to articulate scales, consolidate networks and guide strategic recommendations for public policies.

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1. AmazonFACE Program

Photo: AmazonFACE Program.

AmazonFACE is a scientific research program of the Brazilian Ministry of Science, Technology and Innovation (MCTI) in cooperation with the United Kingdom, whose central feature is a field experiment of unprecedented scale. The experiment uses Free-Air CO₂ Enrichment (FACE) technology to expose an area of mature Amazon rainforest to CO₂ concentrations predicted for future scenarios, at a research station located near Manaus, Brazil.

By allowing direct observation of the Amazon rainforest's responses to the increase in atmospheric CO₂, the AmazonFACE experiment seeks to deepen the understanding of the functioning of the world's largest tropical forest in a context of climate change. In addition to producing scientific knowledge of excellence, the program aims to connect different sciences and co-produce knowledge that guides regional, national and international policies for mitigation and adaptation to climate change, constituting a lasting scientific and institutional legacy.

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In this sense, AmazonFACE recognises that the impacts of climate change and the increase in CO₂ go beyond the biophysical domain, demanding the strengthening of the interface between science, public policies and society, a dimension in which this first workshop was inserted and in which the set of engagement actions provided for in this Executive Summary is inserted.

2. Introduction

This Executive Summary presents the main objectives, approaches, and learnings from the first engagement workshop of the AmazonFACE program dedicated to the interface among science(s), public policy, and society in the context of climate change. The document is aimed at policymakers, opinion leaders and researchers, especially those who participated in the workshop, and aims to systematise the main points of convergence, the challenges identified and the opportunities for progress discussed collectively.

AmazonFACE is an umbrella program that articulates national and international initiatives to understand the impacts of the increase in atmospheric CO₂ and climate change on the Amazon Rainforest and the populations that depend on it. By recognising the socio-ecological complexity of the biome, the program incorporates, from its initial phases, a dimension focused on the science-policy interface, understanding that the social relevance of science depends on its ability to engage with decision-making processes, institutional arrangements and social dynamics.

The first AmazonFACE engagement workshop, held on April 16, 2025, at the MCTI premises in Brasília, represented an inaugural milestone in this effort. The meeting focused on opening a dialogue between scientists and institutional representatives working on climate policies, highlighting both the potential and the challenges of integrating scientific knowledge with public action. The discussions highlighted the

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need to overcome linear models of interaction between science and policy, to strengthen co-production approaches, and to broaden the understanding of science as a strategic resource not only for the design, but also for the implementation, monitoring, and evaluation of public policies.

By recording and systematising the debates of this first moment, this Executive Summary offers a common basis for understanding and trust regarding the interface between science(s), public policies and society within the scope of AmazonFACE. This document thus inaugurates what is intended to be a continuous process of engagement, designed to monitor, inform and qualify public decisions in a context of increasing complexity and climate urgency.

Engaging in this process means strengthening the capacity of the State and society to make evidence-based, socially legitimate, and territorially sensitive decisions, reducing risks, anticipating conflicts, and increasing the effectiveness of public policies. By articulating cutting-edge science, situated knowledge, and political action, AmazonFACE consolidates itself as a strategic platform to transform scientific knowledge into public value, contributing not only to the fight against climate change, but also to the strengthening of democratic governance and the rebuilding of trust between institutions, sciences, and society in Brazil.

Photo: AmazonFACE Program

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3. Methodological Approach to the Workshop

The workshop was conceived based on the understanding of the literature of Social Studies of Science and Technology (STS), which holds that the interface between science(s) and public policies does not operate as a linear process of “evidence transfer” for decision-making. On the contrary, it is a complex, situated, and

frequently disputed field, in which knowledge circulates, is translated, negotiated, and reinterpreted in the midst of different interests, institutional temporalities, and power asymmetries (Duarte, 2023; Fleury et al., 2019; S. Jasanoff, 2004; S. S. Jasanoff, 1987; Pielke, 2007). In the Brazilian context, research indicates that scientific evidence can be part of political agendas and specific institutional arrangements (Lahsen, 2009; Miguel & Velho, 2013; Rajão et al., 2022).

Based on this framework, the workshop adopted a participatory and transdisciplinary approach, conceived as a first step in an engagement process that seeks to co-produce, in the medium and long term, actionable knowledge not only on substantive contents, such as climate change, but also on the social and institutional mechanisms that condition the incorporation (or not) of science into public policies. Methodologically, the workshop combined instruments capable of mapping, in a structured way and without reducing their complexity, actors, relationships and dynamics of the science-politics interface.

Considering its inaugural character, the main objective of the workshop was not to collect data, but to open and qualify the dialogue among scientists, institutional representatives and actors working on climate policies, allowing for the exploration of both the potential and the challenges of articulating scientific knowledge with public action. This approach lays the foundation for a continuous process of learning, co-production, and strengthening the interface between science(s), public policies, and society within the scope of AmazonFACE.

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About Recruiting and Event Preparation

The preparation of the workshop began, as a first methodological step, with a strategic reflection on who the main interlocutors would be and how to establish an initial qualified approximation between government actors and the scientific community. The event was conceived as a first initiative in structured dialogue between representatives of public policy and scientists, involving both members of AmazonFACE and prominent researchers active in the national and international climate agenda.

The main criterion for identifying potential stakeholders was their direct involvement in federal government policies aimed at mitigating and adapting to climate change and other ecological crises. Based on this criterion, the recruitment combined two complementary methods: (i) a systematic mapping of stakeholders via official websites of the federal government and ministries with agendas related to climate policy; and (ii) nominations and invitations institutionally supported by the Ministry of Science, Technology and Innovation (MCTI), co-organiser of the event.

The stakeholder mapping was organised around three main thematic axes: climate crisis, biodiversity and bioeconomy, covering all related ministries and federal agencies. As a result, important actors were highlighted in the Ministry of the Environment and Climate Change, the Ministry of Science, Technology and Innovation, and the National Environment System (SISNAMA), including both advisory and deliberative bodies, such as the National Council for the Environment (CONAMA), and executing agencies, such as IBAMA - The Brazilian Institute of Environment and Renewable Natural Resources and ICMBio - The Chico Mendes Institute for Biodiversity Conservation.

Within this group, the departments linked to the National Secretariat for Climate Change (SMC) stand out, especially the Department of Support to the National Council on Climate Change (DCOL) and the Department of Mitigation and

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Adaptation Policies (DPMA). Another highly relevant collegiate in which stakeholders were mapped was the Interministerial Committee on Climate Change (CIM), due to its centrality in the interministerial articulation of the climate agenda.

The invited speakers' names came mainly from the CIM. We sent invitations to the ministries and agencies, which then curated the list of guests for the morning speeches. All of these participants were asked to share their needs for science from the perspective of their policy work. The concept of the workshop was precisely to open a space for scientists to listen to these demands and respond to them in the afternoon session. Although not all the talks followed this script, we still obtained valuable information about these needs throughout the event. The broader mapping exercise helped identify potential audience members to invite to the event. In addition to these stakeholders, the event was publicised on MCTI's own networks.

From our initial mapping, 118 people were identified. Among these, 85 received a formal invitation by e-mail, with information about the project, the workshop objectives and the exploratory and inaugural nature of the event. Considering the physical capacity of the auditorium, the initial invitations were limited, prioritising holders of strategic positions.

The final list of expected participants included those who responded positively to the invitation sent by e-mail, and those whom the MCTI directly invited. On the day of the event, attendance included both previously registered participants and individuals who, despite not being formally registered, attended and expressed interest in the discussions. This outcome highlights the initiative's relevance and the institutional interest it generated.

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Photo: AmazonFACE Program

4. Key Highlights

The first AmazonFACE workshop dedicated to the science-policy interface fulfilled an inaugural strategic function: to open dialogue across different sectors of the federal government, to make expectations, languages and initial framing assumptions visible, and to signal how the science produced within the scope of AmazonFACE begins to position itself in the public and decision-making spaces. The event's agenda can be found at the end of this document, in Annexe 1.

The highlights presented below are not the result of a formal analysis of data, but result from a process of qualified observation, listening to the interventions made during the event and revisiting the audiovisual record, which allowed the identification of recurrent patterns in the speeches, convergences of understanding, as well as gaps and tensions that are still little explained.

From this interpretative reading, it was possible to identify shared trends among the participants, as well as strategic opportunities for strengthening the science(s)-

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policy-society interface within the scope of AmazonFACE. These highlights thus serve as a basis to guide critical reflections, methodological adjustments, and the next steps of the engagement process, including the subsequent steps planned.

Shared initial framing assumptions:

The presentations and debates revealed a set of understandings shared among the participants, in which the following stand out:

- Shared overall perception of the centrality of science as a basis for effective climate policies, with a strong emphasis on robust data, monitoring and scientific evidence;
- Recognition of the strategic relevance of the Amazon for the national and international climate agenda, both in terms of mitigation and adaptation;
- Understanding of the science-policy interface, predominantly, as a challenge of communication, institutional coordination and translation of scientific knowledge for decision-making;
- Recognition that the territories and knowledge of Indigenous Peoples, Quilombolas, Traditional Peoples and Communities, and Local Communities are not only affected by climate change but also constitute an active and strategic part of mitigation and adaptation solutions, being central to any effective climate policy.

Limits and gaps

Among them, the following stand out:

- The predominance of a perception that the interface between science and politics is linear and technocratic, in which science appears above all as the sole producer of evidence, to be later used by politics;
- A governance approach treated mostly in formalistic and technocratic terms, with less attention to social dimensions, power asymmetries related to race and gender, territorial, political and ethical;

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- The Amazon has often been framed as a passive object of knowledge and management, rather than as a political subject-territory alive and lived by many peoples and their knowledge;
- Little problematisation about who defines scientific questions and based on which interests (reinforcing the technocratic character of governance);
- Still limited insertion of indigenous, traditional and local sciences as a constitutive part, and not just complementary or consultative, of the interface between knowledge and public policies;
- Low explanation of the history of socio-environmental conflicts, power asymmetries and disputes that cross decisions on climate and forest, both on a regional and national scale.

Strategic opportunities identified

From these frameworks and gaps, the workshop made it possible to identify clear opportunities for advancement, which guide AmazonFACE's next steps at the science(s)-policy-society interface:

- Critically analyse the initial framework, making explicit assumptions, languages and logics that shape the dialogue between science and politics;
- Expand the understanding of the science-policy interface, moving it from a linear model (production → use) to a processual, relational and co-produced approach;
- Move beyond strategies focused on the dissemination of results to embrace processes of knowledge co-production, involving decision-makers, public managers and territorial actors from the definition of problems and priorities;
- Reframing the Amazon, moving from seeing the territory as an object of intervention to understanding it as a political, social, and ontological subject, integrating local ways of life, experiences, and knowledge as structuring elements of climate governance;

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- Move away from purely technical governance to more reflective governance, explicitly incorporating conflicts, uncertainties, and inequalities as constitutive components, rather than obstacles, of climate policies;
- Recognise science as a situated practice, with political, ethical, and territorial implications, strengthening its social legitimacy and public relevance.

Overall, there is a great opportunity to broaden the governance approach beyond predominantly technocratic and institutional arrangements, explicitly incorporating the social, territorial, political, and ethical dimensions of climate change, as well as power asymmetries related to race and gender, to strengthen the legitimacy, justice, and effectiveness of public policies.

5. Next Steps

The first workshop highlighted the necessity of maintaining and institutionalising dialogue among scientific communities, public policy makers, and society, rather than limiting engagement to isolated events or political opportunities. There was consensus among participants that the strategic value of AmazonFACE lies not only in the production of cutting-edge science but, above all, in its ability to sustain, over time, spaces for listening, translation, and co-production, thereby strengthening relationships among science, public institutions, and society.

To this end, AmazonFACE has initiated a structured medium-term engagement process, which will be conducted over the next two years through a thematic postdoctoral research project dedicated to monitoring, analysing, and strengthening the science-policy-society interface within the program. This research adopts a transdisciplinary, qualitative and multi-method approach, combining ethnography, interviews with scientists, public managers and social representatives, documentary analysis, participant observation and participatory methodologies. The focus is to understand how scientific evidence circulates, is mobilised,

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reinterpreted or contested, and how it can influence, or fail to influence, decision-making processes at a crucial moment for the future of the Amazon.

The multi-localised nature of the ethnography will allow us to follow the experiment and its institutional developments in different contexts and scales, including Manaus, Campinas, and Brasília, capturing both formal and informal interactions that shape the science-policy interface. The first of these developments will involve a face-to-face workshop in Manaus, during the first half of 2026, engaging local and regional actors. Unlike the inaugural workshop, this stage will explicitly aim to generate qualitative data to assess perceptions regarding the future of the Amazon in the context of climate change and the science-policy-society interface. And a subsequent workshop in Brasília, in 2027, will present the results of the second workshop and connect local and regional actors with those active at the national level.

In addition to specific results, the objective is to establish lasting foundations for continuous processes of transdisciplinary co-production of knowledge and political engagement, promoting closer ties between science, communities, institutions, and politics, and contributing to the construction of fairer, more resilient, and plural futures for the Amazon.

Opening of the Engagement Workshop: Science and Policy in Climate Change - the case of the AmazonFACE Program. Photo: Luara Baggi (ASCOM/MCTI).

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Schedule:

Year	Landmark / Venue	Focus	Key activities	Deliverables / Results
2025	1st Workshop – Brasília (April)	Opening the science(s) – policy – society interface	Inaugural dialogue between public policy stakeholders and scientists from the AmazonFACE program; identification of frameworks, expectations, gaps and opportunities; Alignment over interface nonlinearity	Common basis of understanding; initial continuity agenda; strengthening of networks and institutional dialogue
2025 2027	Postdoctoral research (multiscale: Manaus – Campinas – Brasília)	Monitoring and qualification of the engagement process	Multi-localised ethnography; interviews; document analysis; participant observation; Continuous mapping of dynamics and circulation of evidence	Analytical inputs on the science-policy interface; systematisation of learning; Preparation of upcoming engagements
2026	2nd Workshop – Manaus (planned)	Territorial deepening (Amazonia)	Net-Map for mapping/participatory selection of interlocutors; 3H-CLD workshop to explore desired futures, challenges and transition paths	Qualitative data and visual materials (maps/CLDs); territorial diagnosis; Identifying barriers and leverage points for climate policies
2027	3rd Workshop – Brasília (planned)	Consolidation and national articulation	Synthesis of findings (institutional + territorial); articulation between scales; dialogue with policymakers; Institutionalisation of the process	Policy brief(s) and strategic recommendations; network consolidation; post-2027 continuity agenda

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Annexe 1.

AmazonFACE Program Research Area 5 - Socio-environmental

Engagement Workshop: Science and Policy in Climate Change - the case of the AmazonFACE Program

Date: April 16, 2025

Schedule: 9:00 a.m. to 5:00 p.m.

Location: MCTI Auditorium, Brasilia, Brazil

Support: MCTI (Brazil), MetOffice (United Kingdom)

Workshop Themes

- Bringing science and policy closer together to strengthen the positive impacts of the AmazonFACE Program in Brazil and abroad
- Helping AmazonFACE produce usable and actionable knowledge for policy
- To expand knowledge about the AmazonFACE program in Brazilian political circles
- Present AmazonFACE scientists with concerns and policy actors
- Open opportunities for AmazonFACE research on the science-policy interface

Organising Committee:

Marko Monteiro (UNICAMP)

Marcio Rojas (MCTI)

Marisol Marini (USP)

Poliana Martins (UNICAMP)

Maria Clara Ferreira Guimarães (UNICAMP)

Support:

MCTI (Brazil), MetOffice (United Kingdom)

Workshop Program

8:30 a.m. – Reception and Registration

- a) Reception of participants and distribution of event materials
- b) Coffee

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9:00 a.m. – Official Opening

- **Speakers:**
 - Coordination of the AmazonFACE Program and the Socio-Environmental Area - Carlos Alberto Nobre Quesada (INPA), Maira Padgurschi (CNPEN)
 - Ministry of Science, Technology and Innovation of Brazil – Andrea Latgé (Secretariat of Strategic Policies and Programs of the MCTI)
 - Chief of Staff - Adriano Santhiago de Oliveira, Secretariat of Articulation and Monitoring
 - Embassy of the United Kingdom in Brazil - Tony Kay, Deputy Ambassador of the British Embassy in Brasilia
 - CCC – UK Climate Change Committee – Richard Betts; IPCC contributor, UK Climate Change Risk Assessment and AmazonFACE
- **Estimated time:** 30 minutes
- **Objective:** To present the objectives of the event and highlight the importance of collaboration between science and policy for the Brazilian and global climate agendas. Briefly present the AmazonFACE program and the scope of Brazil-UK cooperation in research.

9:30 a.m. – Opening lectures

- **Theme:** “The Interface between Science and Policy in the Fight against Climate Change”
- **Speakers:**
 - or **Mercedes Bustamante** – University of Brasília - UnB
 - or **Richard Betts** - University of Exeter/Met Office, UK
- **Estimated time:** 1 hour (20 min for each keynote speaker, 20 min for comments/questions)
- **Objective:** To present complementary views on how science and policy interact in tackling climate change, providing a conceptual and practical basis for debates throughout the day

10:30 am – Coffee break

10:50 a.m. – Panel 1: Needs of Public Policy and the Science of Climate Change

- 1) **Theme:** “What are the perceptions and needs of political actors with regard to scientific knowledge about climate change?”
 - 1) **Format:** Panel participants from different policy areas will briefly present (5 min each) information on how they relate to scientific information; how this information is obtained; how they relate to scientists; and what gaps they perceive in this relationship with scientists and science.
- **Participants:**
 - Ministry of Agriculture and Livestock - Rodrigo Dantas (General Coordinator of Low Carbon Emission Agriculture at MAPA)
 - Ministry of Cities - Taís Furtado Pontes (General Coordinator - General Coordination for the Adaptation of Cities to Climate Change - CGMC/DAC/SNDUM)
 - Ministry of Environment and Climate Change – Inamara Mélo (Director of the Department of Policies for Adaptation and Resilience to Climate Change, SMC/MMA)

- Ministry of Indigenous Peoples - Ricardo Neves Romcy Pereira (General Coordinator for the Promotion of Indigenous Good Living - CGPB)
 - Ministry of Development, Industry, Commerce and Services - Edgar Luiz Rodrigues (General Coordinator of Genetic Heritage)
 - Ministry of Finance – Julia Mascarello (General Coordinator of Productive Structure and Sustainability)
 - Ministry of Integration and Regional Development - Armin Augusto Braun (Director of the National Center for Risk and Disaster Management - Cenad/National Secretariat for Civil Protection and Defense)
 - Ministry of Agrarian Development and Family Agriculture - Ernesto Galindo (Deputy Director of the Department of Evaluation, Monitoring, Studies and Strategic Information - DAMEI/SE/MDA)
 - Ministry of Mines and Energy - Sérgio Ayrimoraes (General Coordinator of the Department of Information, Studies and Energy Efficiency of the Ministry of Mines and Energy)
 - Ministry of Planning and Budget - Fabiano Chaves da Silva (Undersecretary of Long-Term Planning)
 - Ministry of Foreign Affairs - Pedro Ivo Ferraz da Silva (Coordinator of Science and Technology and bilateral relations/Department of Climate)
- **Estimated time:** 1 hour and 50 minutes total (5 minutes for each presenter; 20 minutes for discussion/moderated synthesis)
 - **Moderators:** Marcio Rojas (MCTI), Marko Monteiro (Unicamp)

12:40 p.m. – Lunch break

2:00 p.m. – Considerations by Minister Luciana Santos – Ministry of Science and Technology

2:30 p.m. - Panel 2: The AmazonFACE program and its applicability to Climate Change policies

- **Theme:** Main areas of the AmazonFACE program, its results and how they understand the impact and interface with public policy
- **Format:** Panel with senior scientists from AmazonFACE (10 minutes of speech for each): David Lapola (Cepagri/Unicamp), Carlos Alberto Nobre Quesada (INPA), Tomas Ferreira Domingues (USP), Maíra de Campos Gorgulho Padgurschi (CNPEN), Thiago Mota Cardoso (UFAM), Simone Vieira (UNICAMP)
- **Discussion:**
 - or Presentation of the main research areas and results of the AmazonFACE project
 - or How do scientists understand the political demands and concerns presented during the morning? How can your research areas contribute to meeting these needs? What gaps still exist in this interaction between science and politics? Are there points of disagreement or misinterpretations that need to be discussed more directly in the future?
- **Estimated time:** 90 minutes (60 minutes for AmazonFACE researchers and 30 minutes for moderated discussion)
- 1) **Moderator:** Marko Monteiro

4:00 p.m. – Q&A and interactions

- **Format:** Open space for government representatives to ask questions to the scientists of the AmazonFACE project and vice versa.

- **Estimated time:** 30 minutes

4:30 p.m. – Coffee break

5:00 p.m. – Round Table: Synthesis and Next Steps

- **Participants:**
 - or Representatives of the participating ministries (20 minutes)
 - or AmazonFACE researchers and moderators of previous panels (20 minutes)
- **Objective:** To promote greater interaction between political agents and scientists. Each policy participant will be invited to share the main conclusions of the event, also trying to point out opportunities for cooperation and gaps in their interface with science. AmazonFACE's leading scientists will share key findings, how they understand policy needs, and how they can contribute.
- 8. **Estimated time:** 40 minutes

5:40 p.m. – Closing of the Event

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